

Quasithermal Noise in Magnetized Plasma: Theory and Simulations

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Abstract

Quasithermal noise (QTN) spectroscopy has been extensively used as an accurate tool to measure electron density and temperature in unmagnetized space plasmas. The observed spectrum depends on both antenna geometry and plasma kinetic properties. When considering the QTN signal of a magnetized plasma, the description becomes more complicated. We utilize particle-in-cell (PIC) simulations to study the QTN characteristics in magnetized plasmas based on Maxwellian and two-Maxwellian distributions. We compare these results with numerical computations, finding good agreement between the two. However, there are some minor differences. Specifically, when the angle between the wavevector (k) and the background magnetic field was 60° , clear harmonics appeared in the QTN signal from the numerical computations, whereas in the PIC simulations, these harmonics appeared at an angle of 80° . This discrepancy may be related to additional noise in the PIC simulation and our parameter limitations. In addition, Bernstein harmonics become more pronounced as the angle increases between k and the background magnetic field. These results demonstrate that PIC simulations can be used to more accurately characterize QTN signals in complex, magnetized systems.

Unified Astronomy Thesaurus concepts: [Space plasmas \(1544\)](#)

1. Introduction

Understanding the physics of the solar wind and other weakly collisional plasma environments depends on high-quality in situ measurements of electron and ion parameters. Quasithermal noise (QTN) spectroscopy, theoretically described more than half a century ago (J. Fejer & J. Kan 1969), has proven to be a valuable technique for diagnosing space plasma properties. This method utilizes a passive electric antenna connected to a sensitive radio receiver to measure plasma properties. Quasithermal motions of plasma particles trigger spontaneous emission and reabsorption (or induced emission) of random electromagnetic field fluctuations that are fully determined by the velocity distributions of plasma particles, and are then possible to measure with radio antennas (N. Meyer-Vernet 1979; N. Meyer-Vernet & C. Perche 1989; S. Hoang et al. 1993; M. Maksimovic et al. 1995; K. Issautier et al. 1998; M. Moncuquet et al. 2005). Specifically, the QTN spectroscopy enables us to determine macroscopic parameters such as plasma density and temperature profiles from in situ measurements of electrostatic noise (N. Meyer-Vernet & C. Perche 1989; Y. F. Chateau & N. Meyer-Vernet 1991; S. Hoang et al. 1993; K. Issautier et al. 1998; M. Moncuquet et al. 2005; I. Zouganelis 2008; G. Le Chat et al. 2009). Since its pioneering use on board ISEE-3 (N. Meyer-Vernet 1979; S. Hoang et al.

1980), it has been routinely used to infer in situ electron densities and temperatures on various missions in the solar wind: Parker Solar Probe (S. Bale et al. 2016; M. Pulupa et al. 2017; M. Moncuquet et al. 2020; X. Zheng et al. 2024a; 2024b), Solar Orbiter (W. Pansar 2013; M. Maksimovic et al. 2020), IMP-6 (P. J. Kellogg 1981), Ulysses (M. Maksimovic et al. 1995; K. Issautier et al. 1996; K. Issautier et al. 1999; G. Le Chat et al. 2011), Wind (M. Maksimovic et al. 1998; K. Issautier et al. 2005; M. M. Martinović et al. 2020), STEREO (I. Zouganelis et al. 2010; M. Martinović et al. 2016), and planetary missions such as Cassini (M. Moncuquet et al. 2005).

Electrostatic electron Bernstein waves (EBWs) or electron cyclotron harmonic waves are observed in the magnetospheres of Earth, Jupiter, and Saturn (D. A. Gurnett et al. 2005), occurring in bands between the harmonics (n) of electron cyclotron gyrofrequency ($f_{ce} = \frac{eB}{2\pi m_e}$), with the dominant wave power near $(n + 1/2) f_{ce}$ (R. Horne et al. 2003). EBWs propagate nearly perpendicularly to the ambient magnetic field (D. A. Gurnett & A. Bhattacharjee 2005). Via cyclotron resonant interactions, EBWs can pitch angle scatter plasma-sheet electrons into the loss cone in the terrestrial magnetosphere, leading to the excitation of diffuse auroral emissions (R. Horne et al. 2003). Electron scattering by EBWs is also considered as an important mechanism for producing diffuse aurora at Saturn (A. K. Tripathi et al. 2018). Similar weakly banded emissions have been observed in the magnetospheres of Earth (R. R. Shaw & D. A. Gurnett 1975; P. Christiansen et al. 1979), Jupiter (W. Kurth et al. 1980), Saturn (W. Kurth et al. 1983), and Uranus (W. Kurth et al. 1987), and in the Io plasma

torus (T. Birmingham et al. 1981). These emissions are commonly referred to as “ $(n + 1/2)f_{ce}$ ” emissions, although their maximum amplitude is not necessarily observed at the center of the band. While they have often been attributed to plasma instabilities, D. Sentman (1982) demonstrated that, at least for those observed in Earth’s dayside magnetosphere, they can be interpreted as quasithermal fluctuations in Bernstein waves. Certain missions, such as Cassini (D. A. Gurnett et al. 2004), allow electric field probes to access the planet’s magnetosphere. These regions are replete with high-frequency electromagnetic noise, with peak frequency near the upper hybrid frequency (W. Kurth et al. 2015).

In this paper we focus on PIC simulations of spontaneous emission by thermal particles in magnetized plasmas. Even though the fundamental theory is already available in the literature (A. Sitenko 2012) and previous results are available on the upper hybrid waves and energetic electrons in the radiation belts (P. H. Yoon et al. 2017), the detailed exposition on the spectral characteristics associated with multiharmonic cyclotron emission and upper hybrid frequency requires more extensive description. Here, we will investigate the QTN of magnetized plasma by numerical calculations (theory) and PIC simulations, which lays the foundation for the subsequent study of the QTN signals of magnetized plasma. The comparison to PIC simulations is necessary because, while theoretical calculations provide a good approximation of the system’s behavior, they often rely on simplifying assumptions that may not fully capture the complexities of real-world, dynamic plasma conditions. PIC simulations, on the other hand, take into account the kinetic nature of the plasma and can simulate more realistic, nonideal scenarios, including the effects of inhomogeneities, noise, and interactions between particles and fields. Therefore, comparing theoretical results with PIC simulations helps to validate the models and ensure that the theoretical predictions are consistent with more comprehensive, numerically simulated behaviors. This paper is as follows: Section 2 introduces the field fluctuation forms of single Maxwellian and two-Maxwellian electrons in thermal plasma and presents the corresponding PIC simulation setup. Section 3 focuses on the QTN results of magnetized plasma and analyzes the effects of suprathermal electron density and temperature on both QTN theory and PIC results. Section 4 summarizes the characteristics of magnetized plasma and discusses its potential future applications.

2. Methodology

2.1. Spontaneously Emitted Electron Field Fluctuations from Thermal Plasma

2.1.1. Single Maxwellian Plasma

The theory of spontaneous thermal emission of electrostatic fluctuations, including QTN in magnetized plasmas, is discussed in detail in works such as Y. L. Klimontovich (2013) and the seminal paper by D. Sentman (1982). For completeness, we briefly review the formulation here. We begin by considering the linearized Klimontovich equation for magnetized plasmas under the electrostatic approximation. We model the total electron distribution function as a Maxwellian velocity distribution function (VDF). Before applying this formalism to situations relevant to the magnetosphere’s environment, we first examine the ideal case of a single

electron component with a thermal equilibrium VDF,

$$f_e(v) = \frac{n_c}{\pi^{3/2} a_c^3} \exp\left(-\frac{v^2}{a_c^2}\right), \quad (1)$$

where n_c is the density of the particles in the plasma, v is the velocity, and a_c is the thermal velocity. In this step, we will ignore suprathermal electrons. By using this model, we obtain plasma fluctuations of the form

$$\langle \delta E^2 \rangle = \sum_{a=c} \frac{T_a}{\pi^{5/2} \omega} \frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{|\epsilon(k, \omega)|^2} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \xi_a I_n(\lambda_a) e^{-\lambda_a} \exp(-\zeta_n^2 a^2) \quad (2)$$

$$\lambda_a = \frac{k_{\perp}^2 \alpha_a^2}{2\Omega_{ce}^2}, \quad \xi_a = \frac{\omega}{k_{\parallel} \alpha_a}, \quad \zeta_n^2 = \frac{\omega - n\Omega_{ce}}{k_{\parallel} \alpha_a}, \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha_a = \sqrt{2k_B T/m_e}$ is the thermal velocity; k_B represents the Boltzmann constant; k_{\parallel} represents the parallel component of the wavevector k ; ω_{pe} is the plasma oscillation angular frequency; Ω_{ce} presents electron cyclotron frequency; T_a is the temperature of the electrons; $\epsilon(k, \omega)$ is the longitudinal dielectric tensor; and I_n represents the modified Bessel function. Therefore, we can establish the relationship between the wave electric field and the dielectric tensor for the single Maxwellian VDF,

$$(2\pi)^4 \langle \delta E^2 \rangle_{k, \omega} = \frac{8\pi T \operatorname{Im} \epsilon(k, \omega)}{\omega |\epsilon(k, \omega)|^2}. \quad (4)$$

For clearer comparison, we defined the normalized spectral function, and its expression is

$$S(k, \theta, \omega) = \frac{2\pi^3 \omega_{pe} \langle \delta E^2 \rangle_{k, \omega}}{T (cB)^2}. \quad (5)$$

In this equation, c represents the speed of light, and B represents the background magnetic field. This expression indicates that, in the PIC and numerical simulations, we utilized the normalized electric field power spectrum as the output.

2.1.2. Two-Maxwellian Plasma

For multiple electron components the more general equation must be employed in order to compute the spectrum of electrostatic fluctuations. The normalized electric field intensity spectrum is given by P. H. Yoon et al. (2017). We recall here the full expression:

$$\langle \delta E^2 \rangle = \sum_{a=c, h} \frac{T_a}{\pi^{5/2} \omega} \frac{n_a}{|\epsilon(k, \omega)|^2} \frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{n_0 k^2 \alpha_a^2} \times \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \xi_a I_n(\lambda_a) e^{-\lambda_a} \exp(-\zeta_n^2 a^2), \quad (6)$$

where c is the core and the h is the halo electrons (J. B. Abraham et al. 2022). It is convenient to adopt the

Table 1
The PIC Simulation Input Parameters

m_i/m_e	β	ω_{pe}/Ω_{ce}	n_h/n_c	T_h/T_c	Particles per Cell
100	0.01	5	0.1	6	5000

following dimensionless quantities:

$$\begin{aligned}
S(z, q, \theta) &\equiv \frac{2\pi\omega_{pe}}{T_c} \frac{\langle \delta E^2 \rangle_{k, \omega}}{(cB)^2} = \frac{2\pi^{1/2}\rho^3 q^3 \cos \theta}{(cB)^2 |\epsilon(z, q, \theta)|^2} \\
&\quad \times \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \left[(1 - \delta) \Lambda_n(\lambda) e^{-\zeta_n^2} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{\delta}{\tau^{1/2}} \Lambda_n(\tau\lambda) \exp\left(-\frac{\zeta_n^2}{\tau}\right) \right], \\
\epsilon(z, q, \theta) &= q \cos \theta \left[q^2 + 2\rho^2 \left(1 - \delta + \frac{\delta}{\tau}\right) \right] \\
&\quad + 2\rho^2 z \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \left[(1 - \delta) \Lambda_n(\lambda) Z(\zeta_n) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{\delta}{\tau^{1/2}} \Lambda_n(\tau\lambda) Z\left(\frac{\zeta_n}{\tau^{1/2}}\right) \right], \quad (7) \\
z &= \frac{\omega}{\Omega_{ce}}, \quad \rho = \frac{\omega_{pe}}{\Omega_{ce}}, \quad \tau = \frac{T_h}{T_c}, \quad \delta = \frac{n_h}{n_0}, \quad q = \frac{k\alpha_c}{\Omega_{ce}}, \\
\lambda &= \frac{q^2 \sin^2 \theta}{2}, \quad \Lambda_n(\lambda) = I_n(\lambda) e^{-\lambda}, \quad \xi_a = \frac{z}{q \cos \theta}, \quad \zeta_n = \frac{z - n}{q \cos \theta}, \quad (8)
\end{aligned}$$

where $n_0 = n_c + n_h$ is the total electron number density, and $\alpha_h = \sqrt{2K_B T_h / m_e}$ is the suprathermal electron thermal speed.

2.2. The PIC Simulation in QTN

After performing the theoretical QTN calculations, it becomes particularly important to compare them with actual observational results to verify their accuracy. However, due to the limitations in the analysis of magnetized plasma data, this comparison is challenging. We propose using particle-in-cell (PIC) simulations as a robust independent verification method to check theoretical calculations. Our study examines the extent to which current computational capabilities allow modeling plasmas with statistical properties analogous to those found in the planetary magnetospheres. While multidimensional plasma simulations at the required time scales and resolutions remain beyond reach, one-dimensional PIC simulations are beginning to exhibit statistical properties comparable to those of real plasmas for the simplified parameters considered here. This progress motivates us to explore the thermodynamic properties of basic simulation plasmas, with the ultimate goal of simulating plasmas similar to those encountered by the Wind mission (K. Issautier et al. 2001a) and Cassini mission (M. Moncuquet et al. 2005).

In this paper, we concentrate on electrostatic waves, as they hold greater significance than electromagnetic waves for thermal noise measurements in space (A. B. Langdon 1970). The simulation focuses on a magnetized electron plasma with single and two-Maxwellian velocity distributions. We use the PIC code described in K. Liu et al. (2011). The simulation parameters used are found in Table 1, and the electric field fluctuations are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 shows the dimensionless spectral function $S(k, \theta, \omega)$, with the horizontal axis defined by the normalized variable $k\lambda_D$, where λ_D is Debye length (which is related to the electron plasma frequency), and the vertical axis defined by the normalized frequency ω/Ω_{ce} . For numerical plot dimensionless input parameter $\omega_{pe}/\Omega_{ce} = 5$ is adopted. Figure 1 panels (A1)–(A4) show $S(k, \theta, \omega)$ for $\theta = 5^\circ, 60^\circ, 80^\circ, 89^\circ$, respectively. For small angle θ , the spontaneously emitted electrostatic fluctuations are enhanced in the vicinity of the normal mode, which is approximately described by the Langmuir wave dispersion relation. The result for $\theta = 5^\circ$ is thus very similar to the situation for unmagnetized plasmas, which is well known in the literature (E. Lund et al. 1994; E. Lund et al. 1996; R. Mace et al. 1998; R. Tautz et al. 2007; P. H. Yoon et al. 2007; R. Schlickeiser & P. Yoon 2012; C. Ruyer et al. 2013). Even for an angle as large as $\theta = 60^\circ$, the spectrum still resembles that of the unmagnetized case, although lower-harmonic electron cyclotron peaks start being visible. For $\theta = 80^\circ$ and 89° , the spontaneously emitted fluctuations are enhanced around multiharmonic electron cyclotron modes or electron Bernstein modes. This is the regime that has not been thoroughly discussed in the literature, despite some early attempts (D. Sentman 1982; N. Meyer-Vernet 1993; M. Moncuquet et al. 1997; K. Issautier et al. 2001b). Figures 1(B1)–(B4) also show the results from PIC simulations with the same input parameters as the above numerical calculations. These results indicate that the PIC simulations are largely consistent with the numerical results, and as the angle increases, the harmonic phenomenon becomes more pronounced.

Figure 1(C) is analogous to Figure 1(A), but the VDF is modeled as a two-Maxwellian distribution. The parameters of the suprathermal electrons are given in Table 1, and are typical values for the solar wind. The results indicate that the addition of suprathermal electrons leads to an enhancement of the electric field fluctuations. In the following sections, we will discuss this phenomenon in more detail. When comparing panels (C) and (A), we observe a clear enhancement in the two-Maxwellian results. Additionally, the PIC results show a slight enhancement when comparing to the single and two-Maxwellian cases, though this difference is not as pronounced as in the numerical results. To further clarify this, we will quantify the power spectrum results in Figure 2.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. General Properties of the Magnetized Plasma QTN Spectrum

To further explore the QTN results in frequency space, we analyze the integration results of the electric field power spectrum in wavevector k -space. We normalized the antenna response function to unity to separately observe the effects of the spectral function. The frequency expression of the electric field power spectral density is derived as

$$V_f = \int_0^\infty dk S(k, \theta, \omega). \quad (9)$$

Figure 2 shows that when the angle θ is less than 5° , the behavior is consistent with the results for weakly magnetized plasma QTN under the Maxwellian distribution. At $\theta = 60^\circ$, numerical calculations reveal the clear appearance of low-frequency harmonics (in Figure 1). As the angle increases, the morphology of the electron QTN power spectrum changes significantly. Compared to the results at $\theta = 60^\circ$, both theoretical calculations and PIC simulations show more pronounced

Figure 1. Panels (A) and (B) (corresponding to columns 1 and 2, respectively): normalized spectral function $S(k, \theta, \omega)$ vs. wavenumber $k\lambda_D/\omega_{pe}$ and normalized frequency ω/Ω_{ce} , for input parameter $\omega_{pe}/\Omega_{ce} = 5$ and for the following angles corresponding to the different rows: (1) $\theta = 5^\circ$, (2) $\theta = 60^\circ$, (3) $\theta = 80^\circ$, (4) $\theta = 89^\circ$ for theory (A) and PIC simulations (B). White dashed line shows the Langmuir wave relation. Panels (C) and (D): same as panels (A) and (B), but showing the dimensionless spectral function for the two-Maxwellian case. A logarithmic scale has been applied to the color bar.

harmonic signals at $\theta = 80^\circ$, with the harmonics tending to develop toward larger k values. At $\theta = 89^\circ$, the integrated power spectrum exhibits a more pronounced comb-tooth structure, indicating that the assumptions about weakly magnetized plasma no longer apply in this case. Systematic full fit of the magnetized QTN is only sporadically applied to data (N. Meyer-Vernet et al. 1993; M. Moncuquet et al. 1997), and its implementation will require including the antenna angular effects, which will be the topic of a follow-up study done by P. Dazzi et al. (2025).

To verify the QTN characteristics via PIC simulations in a magnetized plasma as in Equation (5), we conducted QTN power spectrum calculations in the frequency domain with $\omega_{pe}/\Omega_{ce} = 5$, and the wavevector at various angles θ to the magnetic field. In Figures 2(c) and (d) the black line displays the integrated QTN results when $\theta = 5^\circ$. The analysis shows that these results are consistent with those in Figures 2(a) and (b), indicating almost no visible harmonic signals in the power spectrum. In Figure 2(c), with $\theta = 60^\circ$, although there is a slight difference from Figure 2(a), it is still difficult to detect harmonics, and the minor low-frequency fluctuations are considered to include numerical noise (NN) and simulation noise (SN; M. E. Dieckmann et al. 2004). A more noticeable harmonic enhancement is observed when comparing the red line ($\theta = 60^\circ$) with the black line ($\theta = 5^\circ$), similar to the results shown in Figures 2(a) and (b). The green line on panel (d) presents the calculation results for $\theta = 89^\circ$, showing a very clear harmonic signal. However, the peaks at $\omega = 5\Omega_{ce}$ are barely visible and the QTN power spectrum predominantly shows a monotonically decreasing comb structure.

This comparison reveals that when the angle between the wavevector and the magnetic field is less than 60° , harmonic signals are challenging to observe in the PIC results, but a prominent QTN peak appears at $\omega \approx \omega_p$. When the angle increases to 80° , both PIC simulations and numerical calculations show very clear harmonic signals. When increased further to 89° , the peaks in theory spectra disappear, replaced by a comb-like spectral structure. However, it still exists in the PIC simulation, which may be caused by SN and NN noise. As shown in P. H. Yoon et al. (2017), even at $\theta = 90^\circ$, the theory results also show that the plasma oscillation peak disappears. Numerical calculations confirm that, except for other noise (SN and NN) disturbance, this spectral result aligns with the PIC simulation, showing a comb-tooth-like power spectral density that decreases as the frequency increases.

3.2. The Suprathermal Electron in QTN Spectrum

Because the electron distribution is better described by a two-Maxwellian distribution (Š. Štverák et al. 2009; J. B. Abraham et al. 2022), in this section we will discuss the effects of the additional suprathermal electron population, choosing parameters guided by observations. We choose the density ratio of $n_h/n_0 = 2 \times 10^{-2}$ to 0.1 and different temperature ratios between the hot and the cold electrons of $T_h/T_c = 2-10$, and we calculate the effects of changing nonthermal electron density and temperature. The results are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 shows the k -integrated spectrum results of the influence of suprathermal electrons. In this case, we have selected the same ratio $\omega_{pe}/\Omega_{ce} = 5$ to maintain consistency in

Figure 2. Numerical computation of QTN power spectral density vs. normalized frequency ω/Ω_{ce} curve results. $\omega_{pe}/\Omega_{ce} = 5$, black line $\theta = 5^\circ$, red line $\theta = 60^\circ$, blue line $\theta = 80^\circ$, green line $\theta = 89^\circ$. Panels (a) and (b) show the QTN power spectra based on theoretical calculations for the Maxwellian and two-Maxwellian cases, respectively. Panels (c) and (d) present the QTN power spectra based on PIC simulations for the Maxwellian and two-Maxwellian cases, respectively. The horizontal axis is normalized using ω/Ω_{ce} and keep $\omega_{pe}/\Omega_{ce} = 5$.

input parameters with the previous comparative results. At this point, we chose an angle of $\theta = 80^\circ$, so that the fluctuations are characterized by the upper hybrid mode. The case without hot electrons ($n_h = 0$) is plotted with a yellow curve. In this single-component electron case, the upper hybrid emission is clearly identified by a peak intensity. Below the upper hybrid peak, there are a series of local Bernstein mode emission peaks with multiple harmonics, but above ω_{UH} , the emission intensity drops sharply. For the red curve in (a), which represents the case of $n_h/n_0 = 0.1$ and $T_h/T_c = 4$, the local multiple harmonic peaks below $\omega_{UH} = \sqrt{\omega_{pe}^2 + \Omega_{ce}^2}$ appear quite similar to those of the single-component electrons, indicating that the Bernstein modes below ω_{UH} are largely determined by the background electrons. However, the intensity peak at ω_{UH} and its immediate vicinity is enhanced compared to the single-component electron case. Above ω_{UH} , the spectral intensity increases considerably relative to the single-component electron case, and the fluctuation intensity features a smooth and continuous spectral profile.

In the case of Figure 3(a) for $n_h/n_0 = 0.1$ and $T_h/T_c = 6$ (plotted in blue), the overall spectral profile is quite similar to

that of the red curve, except that the upper hybrid peak is increased by a factor of >2 . Compared to Figure 3(a), in (b) the yellow curve represents the same power spectrum result for the single-component electrons as in Figure 3(a), while the red, blue, green, and purple lines represent the results for different suprathermal electron components. The results in Figures 3(a) and (b) show that when $\omega < \omega_{pe}$ (i.e., $\omega/\Omega_{ce} < 5$), the harmonics in the PIC simulation are much more pronounced than in the theoretical numerical calculation, being roughly 4 times the theoretical value. This is still related to the SN and NN noise in the PIC simulation.

Additionally, we observe that when $\omega > \omega_{pe}$, the power spectrum in the PIC simulation drops very quickly, and the power spectrum intensity becomes lower than the theoretical calculation. Therefore, we hypothesize that the PIC simulation might enhance low-frequency power while reducing high-frequency power. Due to the limitations of the study, we have not conducted a more detailed investigation of this conclusion in this paper.

In Figures 3(c) and (d), we present the results from both numerical calculations and PIC simulations, where the

Figure 3. k -integrated dimensionless spectral function vs. normalized frequency ω/Ω_{ce} for the input parameter $\omega_{pe}/\Omega_{ce} = 5$ and $\theta = 80^\circ$. Panels (a) and (b) show the effects of suprathermal temperature on the PIC QTN and theoretical QTN power spectra, while keeping the suprathermal electron density constant. Panels (c) and (d) illustrate the effects of suprathermal density on the PIC QTN and theoretical QTN power spectra, while keeping the suprathermal electron temperature constant. The text contains detailed parameters.

temperature of the superheated electrons is fixed, and only the density of the suprathermal electrons is varied. The PIC results in Figure 3(c) show that when the suprathermal electron density increases from 0.02 to 0.1, there is no significant increase in the peak intensity of the power spectrum. However, as the density increases, the FWHM of the power spectrum gradually broadens. Figure 3(d) presents the numerical calculation results, which exhibit a similar trend to those in Figure 3(c), and it is the same as previous studies (P. Couturier et al. 1981; G. Le Chat et al. 2010).

Additionally, in this paper, we only discuss the electric field fluctuations from the spontaneous emission in space plasma (N. Meyer-Vernet & M. Moncuquet 2020), without including the antenna response function in magnetized plasma, due to the complexity of this aspect and its being outside the primary focus of this paper. According to previous research results, it can be observed that this response function is closely related not only to the structure of the antenna itself but also to its angle relative to the background magnetic field. A more detailed discussion on this aspect will be presented in future research.

3.3. On the Difference between Theoretical and PIC Noise Levels

We observed that in Figures 2 and 3, the PIC simulation results are larger than the theoretical calculations in $\omega < \omega_{pe}$ and $\omega \approx \omega_{pe}$. The reason for this discrepancy may be related to the NN and SN in PIC simulations, which persist throughout the

Figure 4. The output power spectrum results corresponding to different numbers of particles per cell. The horizontal is normalized using the plasma angular frequency.

simulation. Moreover, as pointed out in Figure 4 of reference M. E. Dieckmann et al. (2004), the SN exhibits an exponential trend as the wavenumber k increases. Therefore, this noise is likely the main cause of the inconsistency between the PIC simulations and the theoretical calculations. Figure 4 shows the

SN and the resulting power spectrum output for different numbers of particles per cell. Due to computational resource limitations, we ultimately chose 5000 particles per cell.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, we investigated the numerical results of QTN in a magnetized plasma and compared them with PIC simulation results under the same conditions. Our findings show that in numerical calculations, as the angle between the wave propagation direction and the background magnetic field increases, particularly beyond 60° , harmonic phenomena emerge. Additionally, near 90° , the electron Bernstein modes become pronounced. There are slight discrepancies between the numerical and PIC simulation results. For example, while numerical calculations show harmonic phenomena at a 60° angle, PIC simulations only clearly reveal them at 80° .

Furthermore, we analyzed QTN characteristics when a two-Maxwellian velocity distribution, including suprathermal electron components, is considered, specifically at an 80° angle between the wavevector and the magnetic field. Our results show that increasing the suprathermal electron temperature leads to a higher QTN signal intensity, while increasing the suprathermal electron density broadens the signals (FWHM) without affecting the signal amplitude.

These findings demonstrate the complexity of QTN signals in magnetized plasmas and highlight the effects of Bernstein waves on the observed spectrum. In this study, we primarily focused on the QTN characteristics of single Maxwellian and two-Maxwellian distributions. Future research will address more complex scenarios that arise from the inclusion of the antenna response determined for each observing instrument separately.

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